

**Preliminary Psychometric Evaluation of the Constructed Awareness Scale (CAS): An
Exploratory Factor Analysis**

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Abstract

This study reports the preliminary development and psychometric results of the Constructed Awareness Scale (CAS), a multidimensional assessment designed to measure orientation styles as theoretically defined in Constructed Awareness (CA). CA is an emerging counseling model that describes experience as constructed from three building blocks: mental, sensation, and external. The CAS was developed and field-tested using recommended instrument development procedures with a sample of 361 participants. Content validity was examined through a panel review using content validity ratios (CVR). Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) produced a factor structure that reflected three domains: Mental Orientation (M), Sensation Orientation (S), and External Orientation (E). Cronbach's alpha (α) and McDonald's omega (ω) coefficients were calculated for each subscale to estimate internal consistency. The final CAS consists of 12 items, four per subscale. These findings represent an initial, exploratory step toward validating the CAS.

Keywords: Constructed Awareness; Constructed Awareness Scale; scale development; exploratory factor analysis; reliability

Preliminary Psychometric Evaluation of the Constructed Awareness Scale (CAS): An Exploratory Factor Analysis

This study introduces the Constructed Awareness Scale (CAS), a multidimensional assessment based on Constructed Awareness (CA; Orr et al., 2024). CA is a psychotherapy model that examines how individuals construct their reality through their thoughts, sensations, and external environment. Drawing from Barrett's (2017) theory of constructed emotion, CA posits that experiences are dynamically constructed by three building blocks: the mental building block (M), the sensation building block (S), and the external building block (E), which form the foundation of CA's theoretical framework (Orr, 2025).

This paper introduces the three principles of CA (See Figure 1), which underpin the theoretical development of the three building blocks, and these three building blocks represent the subdomains of the CAS. Orientation theory, central to CA, suggests that individuals naturally rely on one or more building blocks to regulate and connect with others across various situations (Orr, 2024). CA further proposes that the building blocks combine in six theoretically defined orientation styles (MES, MSE, EMS, ESM, SME, and SEM), which represent distinct patterns of regulation and attunement. These six styles form the CA typology, which we designed the CAS to measure. We developed the CAS as a preliminary step toward examining whether these theoretical orientation styles can be measured by using single-item descriptors, and toward exploring whether the three building blocks show preliminary empirical distinction.

The remainder of this paper (a) outlines CA's core principles, (b) describes CA orientation theory, (c) introduces the CA typology, (d) compares the CAS to traditional typing systems, (e) provides the rationale for the current study, (f) details the method used to develop and pilot the

CAS following recommended procedures for instrument development (DeVellis, 2016; Kyriazos & Stalikas, 2018; Price, 2016), (g) reports the initial exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and reliability rating, and (h) discusses limitations and implications for future research. This study represents an initial empirical step and a call for further research to validate the measure.

Principles of Constructed Awareness

CA relies on three foundational principles (Orr et al., 2024). The first principle is that bringing awareness to a client's experience changes their experience. Some of the more popular and longstanding approaches to psychotherapy rely on the belief that self-control (i.e., the ability to be in command of one's behavior and to restrain or inhibit one's impulses) is essential to changing behavior, thoughts, and emotions (Marcos & Calero-Elvira, 2015). However, CA posits that determination alone is not sufficient for regulating clients (Orr, in press-a). Instead of trying to control what arises for the client, CA proposes that change emerges when the client mindfully observes their inner process. Mindful awareness, defined as paying nonjudgmental attention to the present moment (Bishop et al., 2004), is considered the catalyst for therapeutic change (Orr, in press-a). Unlike other third-wave approaches that emphasize present-moment acceptance more broadly (Hayes et al., 2016; Kabat-Zinn, 2013; Linehan, 2014; Segal et al., 2013), CA directs mindful attention to specific components of consciousness to explore how the client constructs their present experience (Orr, in press-a).

The second principle of CA is that the human experience is comprised of three building blocks: the mental building block (thoughts), the sensation building block (internal sensations), and the external building block (external environment; Orr, 2025). Counselors trained in CA explore how thoughts, sensations, and external perceptions constitute the conscious human experience,

specifically how emotional experiences are constructed. Barrett's (2017) theory of constructed emotion informs CA's organization of experience by positing that instances of emotions are predictive constructs of the brain that occur as needed in the moment based on internal and external stimuli and past experiences. Other clinical models tend to emphasize one primary domain of experience, such as cognitive approaches that emphasize thought (Nakao et al., 2021), somatic approaches that emphasize internal sensations (Levine, 2015; Ogden & Fisher, 2015), and behavioral or exposure-based methods that highlight observable action or environmental cues (Foa et al., 2019). In contrast, CA explicitly organizes experience across three building blocks. CA proposes that expanding awareness of how these building blocks shape clients' reality can support them in regulating and connecting with others (Orr et al., 2024).

CA's third principle is that clients naturally orient their awareness more strongly to one of the three building blocks (Orr, 2025). That is, they rely on one building block more than the others to regulate themselves and connect with the world. This concept serves as the conceptual basis for CA's orientation theory and typology.

CA's Orientation Theory

Orr (2024) first observed clients orienting their awareness toward distinct building blocks during Eye Movement Desensitization and Reprocessing (EMDR; Shapiro, 2017) sessions. The most common question in the EMDR basic protocol is "What are you noticing now?" (Shapiro, 2017). After asking this question in numerous sessions, Orr (2024) noticed that clients responded differently, revealing patterns in how they regulated emotions and processed their experiences. Although anecdotal, these observations led Orr (2024) to theorize that awareness organizes into three domains (mental, sensation, and external), and that clients tend to rely more heavily on one

domain than the others, which later informed the building blocks and orientation theory of CA.

When asked what they noticed, some clients primarily responded with thoughts, relying on logic and reason to regulate their emotions (Orr et al., 2024). These clients reported regulating themselves mentally and preferred intellectual connections, which led Orr (2024) to identify them as mentally oriented. Others demonstrated external orientation, focusing on their surroundings to maintain stability. These clients often restrained or accommodated their responses to maintain relational stability, expressing concerns like, “I’m just worried I’m making you uncomfortable.” Lastly, sensation-oriented clients often expressed themselves physically, crying, trembling, or releasing emotions cathartically. Outside of sessions, they regulated through bodily sensations and movements and preferred physical connections.

These observations led to the conceptualization that thoughts, sensations, and the external environment function as the primary building blocks through which people construct conscious human experience, aligning with Barrett’s (2017) theory of constructed emotion. Barrett’s work supports CA’s conceptual premise that conscious experience is dynamically constructed, and CA builds on this perspective by specifying three distinct building blocks to provide a framework for identifying patterns of regulation and connection.

Orr (2024) initially theorized that helping clients increase awareness of less-developed building blocks might support a fuller experience of self-regulation during EMDR reprocessing. Although he originally intended this insight to complement EMDR therapy, Orr (2024) later recognized that the principles and tenets of CA did not align with EMDR and that CA is not a modification of EMDR (Orr et al., 2024). This insight led to the development of CA as a separate and distinct model.

Orr's (2024) observation that clients tended to rely more heavily on one building block over the others led to the development of CA's orientation theory. This theory suggests that clients organize their awareness around one dominant building block, shaping how they regulate emotions and connect with others (Orr, 2025). For example, clients who are mentally oriented rely primarily on their minds, sensation-oriented clients rely on their bodies, and externally oriented clients rely on their surroundings and the people around them to maintain emotional and relational stability.

CA further proposes that the building blocks can combine in six ways, forming six distinct orientation styles that capture patterns of regulation and attunement (Orr, 2024, 2025). These orientation styles form the CA typology and are what the CAS is designed to measure. Unlike static typologies that identify clients as fixed types (Marston, 1928; Myers, 1962), CA conceptualizes orientation as dynamic, meaning that no one expresses only one orientation pattern and clients can develop awareness of underutilized building blocks to increase flexibility, regulation, and new patterns of orientation (Orr, 2025). The following section introduces the six theoretical orientation styles that compose the CA typology and outlines how the CAS uses these styles as the basis for scoring.

The Constructed Awareness Typology

The CA typology of six orientation styles emerge from the configuration of the three building blocks: mental (M), sensation (S), and external (E; Orr, 2024, 2025; See Figure 2). The building blocks are defined by both *dominance* and *order of dominance*. Dominance refers to which building block a client relies on most in a given moment. Order of dominance refers to the full ranked sequence of reliance from most used to least used. These two concepts together produce

six orientation styles (MES Striving, MSE Thinking, EMS Adapting, ESM Giving, SME Feeling, and SEM Trusting; Orr, 2025). Dominance and order of dominance can shift depending on the context. For example, a client may frequently express an MES style at work, EMS style with loved ones, and MSE style with their family of origin (Orr, 2024).

CA proposes that each orientation style is associated with traits, behaviors, emotional tendencies, regulation strategies, and attachment expressions (Orr, 2024, 2025). However, these patterns are conceptual, not fixed traits. CA treats orientation as dynamic and flexible rather than categorical or static, which aligns with neurobiological models of experience that emphasize fluid, moment-to-moment construction of meaning (Barrett, 2017; Siegel, 2023). As a result, individuals rarely exhibit a single orientation style across all situations, and clients may move between styles depending on environmental demands and internal states.

CA also distinguishes between being *in tune* and being *dissonant* (Orr et al., 2024). In tune describes a balanced state in which a client flexibly accesses and integrates all three building blocks to support regulation and connection. Dissonant describes a state in which a client becomes over-reliant on one building block or the building blocks become unstable (Orr, 2025). Orientation theory's constructs of in tune and dissonance align with Siegel's (2009, 2023) concept of *internal attunement*, which emphasizes maintaining balance and coherence across different aspects of experience. By enhancing awareness of the three building blocks, clients develop a greater capacity to adapt to varying contexts, which facilitates emotional regulation and resilience (Orr, 2024).

Understanding orientation styles provides a conceptual framework for exploring how clients regulate themselves, connect with others, and organize awareness across experiences (Orr, 2025).

Orr (2024) developed the following theoretical descriptions of the orientation styles through clinical observations and refined them through consultation with CA therapists (Orr, 2025). The descriptions illustrate how the theoretical concepts of building blocks and orientations are applied to create specific patterns of regulation and attunement, as printed in Orr (2024).

MES Striving

“When in tune, these individuals are often analytical, assertive, driven, good at developing and following through with plans, decisive, creative, charismatic, and ambitious. When dissonant, they are opinionated, quick-tempered, pushy, over-working, intense, impatient, judgmental, and inflexible (p. 322).”

MSE Thinking

“When in tune, these individuals are often independent, undemanding, intelligent, creative, inquisitive, analytical, thoughtful, empathetic, imaginative, and are often drawn to spirituality, art, philosophy, or fields that involve deep thinking. When dissonant, they are reclusive, detached, unassertive, and prone to dissociation (p. 322).”

SME Feeling

“When in tune, these individuals are often imaginative, creative, empathetic, highly intuitive, caring, loyal, value-oriented, sensitive, shy, and practical. When dissonant, they are emotional, easily rattled or overwhelmed, withdrawn, socially awkward, and possibly prone to self-destructive behaviors (p. 322).”

SEM Trusting

“When in tune, these individuals are often kindhearted, caring, sweet, childlike, endearing,

innocent, empathetic, considerate, and likable. When dissonant, they are helpless, dependent, suggestible, emotional, unreliable, unpredictable, indecisive, and easily overwhelmed (p. 322).”

EMS Adapting

“When in tune, these individuals are often adaptive, extroverted, outgoing, optimistic, versatile, talented, spontaneous, fun, energetic, witty, adventurous, empathetic, charismatic, and charming. When dissonant, they are scattered, undisciplined, impatient, impulsive, distracted, and unable to recognize personal needs (p. 322).”

ESM Giving

“When in tune, these individuals are often accepting, caring, optimistic, generous, nurturing, caregiving, adaptable, peace-making, reliable, responsible, devoted, and loving. When dissonant, they are conflict-avoidant, indecisive, resentful, obligated, self-blaming, self-doubting, and over-accommodating (p. 322).”

Comparing the CA Typology to Traditional Typing Systems

CA typology’s approach to dominance and order of dominance diverges from traditional typologies commonly used in counseling. For example, the Myers-Briggs Type Indicator (MBTI; Myers, 1962) categorizes individuals into 16 types but does not specify which of the four traits is most dominant within the type. An ESTJ, for instance, might function very differently depending on whether Extroversion (E) or Judging (J) is most relied upon in a given context. MBTI does not account for this order of dominance. If it did, each four-letter type would include a ranked order of those traits, which would dramatically increase the number of possible combinations and complicate clinical interpretation.

Similarly, the DISC model (Marston, 1928) identifies a client's highest score as their primary style but does not account for dominance order among the four categories. For instance, a client scored as Steadiness (S) with Influence (I) as secondary would be labeled an SI style. However, DISC does not differentiate whether Conscientiousness (C) or Dominance (D) plays a tertiary role, which could significantly alter interpretations. If DISC accounted for the whole order of dominance, it would result in a much larger set of combinations, limiting its practical use.

In contrast, CA's typology uses only three building blocks to generate six orientation styles based on dominance patterns, offering a concise classification system that still accounts for contextual patterns and flexibility (Orr, 2024). Building on this theoretical framework, the CAS was designed to assess orientation styles and identify patterns of regulation and attunement across contexts. By measuring dominance and order of dominance patterns among the building blocks, the CAS may provide preliminary insight into how individuals organize their experiences, which may inform how they tend to regulate and connect with others.

These limitations in traditional typing systems further support the need for instruments that conceptualize personality as fluid, not fixed. Typological models that type clients can oversimplify complex behaviors and traits, introducing risks such as confirmation bias, reductionism, and myopia, which can potentially lead to misinterpretations of clients' emotional experiences (Hrebinyk, 2019). Viewing types as fixed can also create subtle ethical risks in clinical practice. When a counselor labels a client as a specific type, they may imply that the client fundamentally embodies that trait rather than occasionally expressing it (Anwar & Shah, 2022). Such labeling can lead to misunderstandings, limit therapeutic flexibility, and perpetuate overly simplistic narratives (Acklin, 2018).

By contrast, CA does not assign fixed types to people (Orr, 2025). Rather, CA uses the term orientation style to describe how clients express regulation patterns in context. CA conceptualizes orientation as fluid and context-dependent, reducing the potential for overgeneralization and promoting a more nuanced understanding of clients' experiences. The following section outlines the rationale for developing the CAS and evaluating its initial psychometric properties using EFA and reliability testing.

Rationale for the Current Study

CA orientation theory proposes that awareness organizes around three building blocks: mental (M), sensation (S), and external (E), and that orientation patterns reflect how individuals regulate and connect (Orr et al., 2024). Although these building blocks and their associated styles have been defined conceptually (Orr, 2024, 2025), the theory has not yet been tested empirically and no studies have examined the empirical structure of the three building blocks. The CAS was designed to operationalize orientation theory by assessing dominance and order of dominance across the three building blocks to identify the respondent's orientation style.

The current study provides an initial psychometric evaluation of the CAS by examining whether the items cluster into factors consistent with the three theorized building blocks and by evaluating the internal reliability of those factors. Since CA is the only framework that conceptualizes orientation based on awareness of thoughts, sensation, and external senses, no existing instruments measure this construct. Initial validation of the CAS is therefore necessary before subsequent research can examine its broader validity.

The present study addresses two research questions:

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1. What is the factor structure of the CAS?
2. What is the internal reliability of the CAS subscales?

Method

The current study received IRB approval prior to beginning any research procedures. We developed and field-tested the items for the CAS using theoretical guidelines and recommended instrument development procedures from DeVellis (2016), Kyriazos and Stalikas (2018), and Price (2016). Specifically, we performed the following steps: a) determine what to measure; b) determine the format of the test; c) generate an item pool; d) have the initial item pool reviewed by panelists; e) conduct pilot tests; f) administer items to a development sample; and g) evaluate the items using EFA and reliability testing.

Determine What to Measure

We designed the CAS items to measure three dimensions of orientation associated with the three building blocks. CA defines orientation as the fluid organization and reciprocal interplay of the client's mental, sensation, and external building blocks that shape how the client regulates and connects with others (Orr, 2024). The three subscales of orientation measured by the CAS are Mental Orientation (M), External Orientation (E), and Sensation Orientation (S). Since CA views orientation as fluid, the CAS encourages respondents to complete the assessment in multiple contexts such as work, home, or relationships to identify shifting patterns of strengths and areas for development. This contextual flexibility aligns with state-dependent learning theory, which proposes that an individual's internal state influences how information is encoded, accessed, and recalled across contexts (Bower, 1981).

Determine the Format of the Test

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The CAS is a multidimensional pre-assessment designed to measure orientation. It uses a four-point Likert scale (1 Strongly Disagree; 2 Disagree; 3 Agree; 4 Strongly Agree), with the final version consisting of 12 single-phrase items, four for each orientation, creating subscale ranges of 4 to 16. We selected a four-point scale to avoid a neutral midpoint and encourage respondents to indicate a directional preference. Higher scores on each subscale reflect a stronger tendency to orient to that specific building block. Respondents can complete the assessment in or outside of therapy sessions.

Generate an Item Pool

Kyriazos and Stalikas (2018) recommend generating an item pool of 80–100 Likert items. Following this guideline, we developed an initial pool of 89 items. The items were constructed using a rational/theoretical approach (Ruscio, 2015) grounded in CA orientation theory and descriptions of orientation styles derived from clinical observations of client responses and feedback from CA therapists. The items were not derived from what clients noticed in the building blocks but how they used the building blocks to regulate themselves and connect with others. For example, mental orientation items focused on cognitive strategies such as analyzing situations or problem-solving. Sensation orientation items emphasized physical awareness and internal experiences, including emotional expressions. External orientation items targeted relational and environmental awareness such as attending to people to support regulation and attunement.

Have the Initial Item Pool Reviewed by Panelists

We assembled a 15-member panel to establish content validity. Kyriazos and Stalikas (2018) recommend panels include both content and lay experts. Therefore, we selected panelists from

CA-trained therapists and non-therapists who demonstrated clear alignment with one of the three orientations based on pre-panel interviews. Panelists were 60% female, 33% male, and 7% nonbinary. They identified 79% Caucasian, 7% Native American, 7% Asian/Pacific Islander, and 7% biracial. Their ages ranged from 32 to 67, and represented a mix of professional backgrounds, with 73% being licensed therapists. The therapists who participated in the panel review had completed at least Level 1 CA training (30 hours), which emphasized CA principles, orientation theory, typology, and experiential practice. None of the panelists were CA clients to prevent coercion or conflicts of interest.

We selected panelists based on patterns observed in their descriptions of preferred regulation and connection strategies. For example, mentally oriented panelists frequently emphasized logic, analysis, and problem-solving in their reflections. Externally oriented panelists described prioritizing relationships or surroundings to feel stable or connected, while sensation-oriented panelists highlighted bodily and emotional expression as central to their regulation and attunement strategies.

Panelists rated the items to measure content validity ratio (CVR), using Lawshe's (1975) three-point scale (i.e., 1 = Not Necessary, 2 = Important but not essential, and 3 = Essential).

Additionally, panelists were allowed to respond to each item, and in some instances, we conducted follow-up interviews to clarify items and address questions. From these responses and interviews, four additional items were created, which were also subjected to CVR. Because CA theory specifies that each building block is distinct, we grouped the 15 panelists into three five-member subpanels based on their dominant orientation (Mental, Sensation, External). For each item, we applied Lawshe's critical value for $n = 5$ ($CVR \geq .99$), which required that all five panelists within a subpanel rate the item as 'Essential' for that item to be retained. This process

resulted in 30 retained items (9 Mental, 14 External, and 7 Sensation).

Pilot Testing

After the initial 30 items were confirmed, we conducted five pilot tests using Google Forms to collect and store the data. Barker et al. (2015) suggested using 20–30 participants for pilot studies, which we did for the first three pilots (Pilot 1 $n = 25$; Pilot 2 $n = 26$; Pilot 3 $n = 21$). For the fourth and fifth pilots (Pilot 4 $n = 82$; Pilot 5 $n = 91$), we recruited a minimum of 75 respondents to meet the five-participants-to-one-item rule of thumb for EFA, as recommended by Kline (2016). Using smaller samples allowed us to analyze the data, reevaluate the items, and adjust the number of items where necessary before retesting with larger samples.

During pilot testing, we experimented with both four-point and five-point Likert scales to rate responses (e.g., Very Accurate or Strongly Agree). We ultimately selected a four-point scale to avoid a neutral response, encouraging participants to make a clear choice, as recommended by Nadler et al. (2015). This decision was made to enhance the clarity and decisiveness of the responses.

The majority of pilot participants were White/Caucasian (86.62%), with representation from other ethnicities, including Hispanic/Latino (3.52%) and Black/African American (4.23%) participants. The most common age group was 35-44 (33.10%). Female participants represented 69.72% of the sample, while males made up 24.65%, and nonbinary participants accounted for 4.23%.

We used JASP (2023) to conduct EFAs and calculate Cronbach's alpha (α ; Cronbach, 1951) for internal consistency. Items were evaluated based on factor loadings, with a loading threshold of $\geq .40$ for retention, as suggested by Osborne et al. (2008). Items that failed to meet this threshold or

displayed cross-loadings were removed. In addition to factor loadings, we assessed item–total correlations and retained items that contributed to subscale reliability, aiming for Cronbach’s $\alpha \geq .60$, as recommended by Bernardi (1994), Nunnally (1967), Hulin et al. (2001), and Pallant (2013). This analysis reduced the initial item pool to 15 items, with 5 items per subscale, ready to be administered to a larger sample.

Administer Items to a Development Sample

After completing the pilot testing, we administered the initial 15 items to a larger development sample of three hundred sixty-one ($n = 361$) individuals, which was greater than Comrey and Lee (1992) and Tabachnick and Fidell’s (2012) recommendation of at least 300 respondents for factor analysis. We collected data using a Google Form, which provided a secure system to collect and store data. The form included informed consent, the 15-item CAS, and a demographic questionnaire, in that order.

Participants

Tabachnick and Fidell (2012) recommend a minimum of 300 respondents for factor analysis, and Comrey and Lee (1992) grade a factor analysis sample of 300 as “good.” Therefore, our goal was to recruit a minimum of 300 respondents. Inclusion criteria were: 1) able to give informed consent, 2) at least 18 years of age, and 3) able to speak, read, and write English.

To recruit, we used convenience and snowball sampling by distributing a Google Form link to all CA-trained therapists, inviting them to tell their clients, colleagues, and social networks about the study. No agreements or payments were made to the participants or the CA therapist who recruited the participants. We had no way of tracking which therapists shared the form, and the therapists had no way of tracking who completed the form. This limited the potential for

coercion. All participants completed the same form, which included informed consent, the 15-item CAS, and a demographic questionnaire in that order, and the data-collection period ran for four weeks in September and October 2023.

We originally designed the CAS as a clinical assessment to determine individuals' CA orientation styles. However, we also believe the CAS and the CA typology may have potential utility beyond psychotherapy settings, similar to the MBTI (Myers, 1962), the DISC (Marston, 1928), and the Enneagram (Cusack, 2020). Therefore, we recruited a general sample of adult counseling clients and non-clients. The demographic questionnaire included the question, "Are you currently working with a mental health professional (counselor, social worker, psychologist, marriage and family therapist, psychiatrist, etc.), or have you in the past?" to identify a clinical percentage of the sample.

Evaluate the Items

To address Research Question 1, we used exploratory factor analysis (EFA) to determine the final number of items, estimate the total variance explained by the specific items, and reveal the CAS's underlying factor structure. We used the minimum residual extraction method and a Promax rotation, as the three orientation domains were theoretically expected to be distinct but potentially correlated. A parallel analysis was not conducted, as the goal was to explore the initial factor structure rather than confirm a hypothesized dimensionality. We used JASP (2023) to conduct the EFA. This analysis resulted in a final CAS composition of 12 items (four items per subscale).

To address Research Question 2, we calculated Cronbach's α (Cronbach, 1951) and McDonald's omega (ω ; McDonald, 1999) for the three subscale scores. Cronbach's α assumes that items have

equivalent loadings on the factor, which is rarely the case in psychological measures. In contrast, McDonald's ω provides a congeneric reliability estimate that does not rely on this assumption (Dunn et al., 2014). Reporting both coefficients offers a more complete evaluation of the CAS's internal consistency by allowing comparison across different reliability estimates.

Results

To prepare for analysis, we first screened the data. A total of 371 individuals responded to the survey. We excluded ten responses, resulting in a final sample of 361 participants. Reasons for exclusion included duplicate submissions from the same respondent and failure to meet inclusion criteria. No data were missing. Six participants gave straight-line responses (i.e., selected the same answer for all items), but we retained their responses as Reuning and Plutzer (2020) recommended, since such patterns may still reflect genuine attitudes or consistent opinions rather than disengaged or invalid responses. Table 1 reports the demographic characteristics for the total sample ($n = 361$).

Exploratory Factor Analysis

Prior to conducting the EFA, we examined the data to ensure that statistical assumptions were met. We used skewness and kurtosis to check the normality of the data. George and Mallery (2010) suggest that skewness and kurtosis values between -2 and +2 are acceptable. Table 2 shows that all skewness and kurtosis values fell within -2 and +2, indicating the data was normal. Scatter plots showed positive linear correlations among items within each factor. Inter-item correlations were significant and positively correlated. Also, we adopted Hutcheson and Sofroniou's (1999) recommendation that Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO; Kaiser & Rice, 1974)

values greater than .60 indicate that the sample size was adequate to yield distinct and reliable factors and Bartlett's (1954) recommendation that a significant Bartlett's Test of Sphericity indicates that correlations between items were large enough for factor analysis. KMO test scores ranged from 0.71 to 0.83, with a total score of 0.76, and Bartlett's test showed significance ($p < .001$). Outliers were not removed from the dataset as skewness and kurtosis were between -2 and +2 for all items.

We did not begin with an objective to shorten the CAS. However, we remained open to removing items if they demonstrated low loadings. To evaluate possible item removal, we reviewed the initial structure matrix using Pett et al.'s (2003) recommendations for item deletion. Initially, four factors met the Kaiser (1960) rule of having eigenvalues of 1.00 or greater, with communalities ranging from .39 to .80. To delete items, we a) removed items below a factor loading threshold of .40 and b) reviewed the absolute magnitude of cross-loadings to identify items that loaded at least .15 higher on their primary factor than on any other factor (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2012). Regarding narrower cross-loadings, we considered subscale length and theoretical rationales for item retention.

After deleting an item, we re-ran a new EFA following the same methods. After deleting a total of three items, the fourth factor's eigenvalue fell below 1.00, leading us to eliminate it from inclusion, as recommended by Kaiser (1960) and Pett et al. (2003). The scree plot also supported a three-factor solution (see Figure 3). Removing the fourth factor provided a three-factor final version that met all criteria. Factor correlations ranged from -0.29 to 0.25, indicating modest relationships among the three factors. The three-factor solution accounted for 46% of the total variance in the unrotated solution. Thus, the final scale consisted of 12 items, with Factor 1: Sensation Orientation (S) containing four items (i.e., Emotional, Deep Feeler, Emotive, and

Sensitive), Factor 2: Mental Orientation (M) containing four items (i.e., Logical, Rational, Reasoned, and Analytical), and Factor 3: External Orientation (E) containing four items (i.e., Cooperative, Helpful, Agreeable, and Considerate). See Table 3 for the factor loadings of the final 12 items.

Inter-item correlations within each subscale were positive and significant ($p < .001$). Sensation items correlated moderately to strongly (ranging from 0.32 to 0.59), Mental items correlated moderately to strongly (ranging from 0.30 to 0.61), and External items correlated at small to moderate levels (ranging from 0.27 to 0.46). We did not predict correlations across factors but allowed for their possibility. Some cross-factor relationships emerged. Items from the Mental and Sensation subscales were negatively correlated at small levels (ranging from -0.25 to -0.07), and two External items (Helpful and Considerate) showed small positive correlations with Sensation items (ranging from 0.15 to 0.25).

Reliability

To determine the internal consistency of the CAS, we calculated Cronbach's α and McDonald's ω for each factor derived from the EFA. The Sensation Orientation (S) subscale produced $\alpha = .79$ (95% CI [.76, .83]) and $\omega = .80$ (95% CI [.76, .83]). The Mental Orientation (M) subscale produced $\alpha = .74$ (95% CI [.67, .79]) and $\omega = .74$ (95% CI [.67, .79]). The External Orientation (E) subscale produced $\alpha = .69$ (95% CI [.63, .75]) and $\omega = .70$ (95% CI [.64, .75]).

Discussion

The CAS assesses orientation through three subscales: Mental Orientation (M), Sensation Orientation (S), and External Orientation (E). The CAS is self-administered and self-scored. Although the CAS has no time limit, completion typically takes about three minutes. The final

scale contains 12 Likert-type items with four response options (1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Agree, 4 = Strongly Agree). Each subscale contains four items, creating subscale score ranges of 4 to 16.

Administration of the CAS yields three subscale scores: Mental Orientation (M), Sensation Orientation (S), and External Orientation (E). Respondents sum the four items in each subscale to generate subscale scores. They then rank the three scores from highest to lowest to create a three-letter orientation configuration (e.g., MES).

Preliminary Support for the CAS Structure: CVR and EFA

In this study, we examined content validity and initial construct validity. Panel ratings using Lawshe's (1975) CVR method supported initial content validity of the CAS, indicating that the retained items were consistently judged as essential and represented the intended building block domains. Panel ratings provide initial evidence that the item content reflects the constructs the CAS was designed to measure.

We also explored construct validity through EFA. The final 12-item solution demonstrated a three-factor structure that aligns with the three building blocks central to CA orientation theory. These initial results suggest that the CAS structure reflects the theoretical organization of orientation across the three building blocks. This alignment supports the interpretation that the CAS may measure how individuals use each building block to organize their emotional and relational experience. However, we cannot make this claim with certainty without further research.

Although we designed the CAS to measure three distinct domains, modest inter-factor relationships emerged. Negative correlations between Mental and Sensation items may support

the theory that when individuals rely more on one building block, they rely less on others in different contexts. Small positive correlations between some Sensation and External items suggest a partial overlap between embodied awareness and relational engagement. While these findings were not predicted, they align with CA's conceptualization of orientation as fluid and context-dependent, allowing interaction among the building blocks rather than strict independence.

Reliability

The CAS's subscale scores showed adequate reliability for exploratory purposes. The External Orientation (E) subscale's $\alpha = .69$ falls just below Hair et al.'s (2010) commonly cited .70 guideline. However, Hair et al. (2010) also note that alpha coefficients as low as .60 can be acceptable in exploratory research, which applies to the present study. In addition, values between .60 and .70 are considered acceptable for exploratory research according to Bernardi (1994), Hulin et al. (2001), Nunnally (1967), and Pallant (2013). Given that this is the CAS's first administration, the External Orientation (E) subscale's $\alpha = .69$ may be considered acceptable for early-stage research and warrants further examination in future studies, while the corresponding $\omega = .70$ meets the commonly cited .70 threshold.

We did not report overall reliability coefficients (Cronbach's α or McDonald's ω) because the CAS is intentionally multidimensional rather than unidimensional. The CAS's structure reflects CA's orientation theory, which conceptualizes the Mental Orientation (M), Sensation Orientation (S), and External Orientation (E) factors as distinct yet interrelated domains. Since each subscale represents a separate construct, reliability is evaluated at the subscale level. Widhiarso (2010) noted that total-scale coefficients can underestimate reliability in multidimensional measures,

and Cronbach (1951) similarly recommended calculating alpha only within coherent item sets. McDonald's ω also requires either a single underlying factor or a supported higher-order factor model (Dunn et al., 2014), neither of which the CAS proposes. For these reasons, both Cronbach's α and McDonald's ω were computed only for the three subscales, as overall consistency scores are not informative for this instrument.

Implications for Counseling Practice and Research

We developed the CAS initially as a tool for counselors to identify clients' orientation styles. Understanding the client's orientation styles informs the counselor about which building blocks are most dominant and which are least dominant in given contexts. This knowledge can guide counselors to select resources most appropriate for clients' specific needs. For example, a client who scores MES would likely benefit most from somatic resources, given their low sensation orientation (S). Although we designed the CAS as a therapeutic tool, it may also have potential utility beyond psychotherapy settings, similar to the MBTI (Myers, 1962), the DISC (Marston, 1928), and the Enneagram (Cusack, 2020). However, this possibility requires further research before any conclusions can be drawn.

Because CA conceptualizes orientation as fluid, the CAS can also be completed with different contexts in mind (for example, work, family, friendships). This allows individuals to take the CAS multiple times and compare their orientation patterns across situations. These context-based comparisons can help identify whether the order of the building blocks shifts in different environments and offer preliminary insight into how a person organizes experience across domains. Although the CAS was designed to allow for context-based administration, the

feasibility and psychometric consistency of administering it across multiple contexts have not yet been tested and warrant future study.

Counselors can also use the CAS to understand their own orientation patterns, which can help them strengthen their own building blocks that are less developed. Conscious awareness of one's direct experience is an essential goal for any counselor (Pompeo & Levitt, 2014). Researchers have noted that practicing self-awareness is essential for both counselors and clients when working with certain mental health conditions (Diamond et al., 2003; Layden et al., 1993). Many counselors consider personal self-awareness necessary only to support clients' needs and to enhance therapeutic rapport (La Torre, 2005). However, counselor self-reflection is necessary because counselors also actively participate in the therapeutic relationship (Pompeo & Levitt, 2014). Awareness of their own building blocks can enhance how counselors work with their clients of varying orientation styles and foster positive therapeutic relationships with diverse clients (Orr, 2024, 2025). For example, a primarily mentally-oriented counselor may struggle to understand the experience of and build rapport with a largely sensation-oriented client because the counselor may not naturally relate to how the client regulates and connects with others. If the counselor recognizes they lack somatic awareness and engages in practices to connect more with bodily sensations, they may more effectively meet sensation-oriented clients where they are.

Likewise, we see possibilities for applying the CA typology to clinical supervision. Supervisors may use the CAS to better understand and train supervisees, as some have done with other typologies like the Enneagram (Perryman et al., 2018) and the MBTI (Moore et al., 2004). Lohani and Sharma (2023) find self-awareness to be an essential part of clinical supervision. The three subscales of the CAS may provide clinical supervisors with a unique framework to understand and evaluate supervisees' self-awareness.

Regarding implications for future research, this study established the initial factor structure and reliability of the CAS. Due to the nature of EFA and the limitations discussed below, we urge caution in relying solely on the CAS for high-stakes research or making assumptions about general population normative data. Future research, including confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and additional validity testing, is needed before researchers and counselors can view the CAS as robust.

Limitations

As with any preliminary study of a scale, limitations existed. Our non-random sampling procedure (i.e., convenience and snowball sampling) presented the most obvious limitation, as there was no guarantee that the sample represented the general population, making our findings susceptible to sampling bias. This sampling approach may therefore limit generalizability, and future studies should use more diverse and representative samples. Additionally, though we took care to screen the data, the possibility remains that some respondents did not engage genuinely with the survey.

We used Comrey and Lee's (1992) and Tabachnick and Fidell's (2012) recommendation of a minimum of 300 participants to determine the target sample size for factor analysis. Therefore, our sample ($n = 361$) was adequate for EFA, but not large enough to also conduct CFA on an independent sample to yield convergent and discriminant validity information. We intentionally prioritized EFA in this first study because the scale was in an early development stage, and we wanted to identify the CAS factor structure before testing a hypothesized model. Because this was an exploratory analysis, future research should include CFA to test whether the three-factor

structure replicates in an independent sample.

The content validity process also presents a potential limitation. The reduction from the initial 89 items to the final 12 is substantial. Using Lawshe's (1975) CVR method required unanimous agreement among five reviewers ($CVR \geq .99$), which is a highly restrictive threshold. This requirement may have led to the premature removal of items that could have performed adequately with a larger expert panel or under less restrictive content-validity procedures. Future studies should replicate the content review process with more reviewers and allow for a less stringent cutoff to better evaluate initial item quality.

The External Orientation (E) subscale's alpha of .69 is considered "questionable" by George and Mallery's (2010) guidelines, suggesting that this factor may be less stable than the other two. Further research will be necessary to verify and potentially strengthen the reliability of this subscale, which represents an additional limitation when interpreting the factor structure. Additionally, small positive correlations between two External Orientation (E) items (Helpful and Considerate) and all four Sensation items may indicate a partial overlap between these subscales. Given the External Orientation subscale's borderline reliability, this overlap suggests that the External items may be refined in future versions of the CAS to enhance discriminant validity. Because the External items reflect socially desirable interpersonal traits, future studies should also examine whether External Orientation (E) scores are influenced by social desirability response tendencies.

Another limitation was that the sample was primarily White, cisgender, and educated, as were the researchers. Our recruiting methods may have skewed the sample based on the identities of the researchers and CA-trained therapists who recruited participants. Therefore, further

validation and replication should focus on alternative recruitment methods and recruit from more specific populations to determine the utility of the CAS for general population use and for use with specific populations. Also, self-report and common-method variance may have inflated within-factor correlations. We also retained six straight-line responders; while potentially reflecting genuine consistency, this choice may have slightly biased reliability estimates.

Additionally, our inclusion criteria limited us from understanding the CAS's use with non-English speaking individuals and minors. The CAS is in English, and only English speakers were allowed to participate. Cross-cultural and cross-linguistic applications were beyond the scope of this study. Therefore, our study did not provide information about possible cross-cultural and cross-linguistic biases. In fact, our definition of orientation may have different understandings and expressions across cultures. Thus, using the CAS as a universal scale to measure orientation constructs across all cultures may be inappropriate. Similarly, the study tells us nothing about the CAS's potential for use with minors, as only individuals 18 and older were allowed to participate.

Although the CAS was designed to allow for administration across different contexts (e.g., work, family, relationships), the feasibility and psychometric consistency of using the measure in this manner have not yet been evaluated. Future research should examine whether the CAS maintains reliability and structural integrity when administered across multiple contexts. Finally, the CAS may assist researchers in identifying patterns of orientation; however, the CAS is not designed for diagnostic decision-making and should not be interpreted as a measure of pathology.

To date, two quantitative studies (Orr et al., 2024; Orr & McMahan, 2024) and four conceptual papers (Orr, 2024, 2025; Orr, in press-a, in press-b) have been published or are currently in press

to establish the foundation of the CA orientation framework. While these works provide an initial basis for scale development, we recognize the value of further quantitative, qualitative, and mixed-method research to explore the nuances of the phenomenon. Future research directions include conducting in-depth qualitative studies to examine the lived experiences underlying orientation styles and implementing mixed-method designs to continue validating and refining the theoretical framework.

Conclusion

This study aimed to report on the development of the CAS and evaluate its initial psychometric properties through EFA and reliability testing. Using recommended instrument development procedures from DeVellis (2016), Kyriazos and Stalikas (2018), and Price (2016), and Pett et al.'s (2003) best practices for item and factor retention, we developed a 12-item scale consisting of three factors: Mental Orientation (M), Sensation Orientation (S), and External Orientation (E). Across these three domains, the CAS subscales fell within acceptable reliability ranges cited in the literature (Bernardi, 1994; Nunnally, 1967; Hulin et al., 2001; Pallant, 2013). The External Orientation (E) subscale's $\alpha = .69$ falls slightly below Hair et al.'s (2010) commonly cited .70 guideline, yet both $\alpha = .69$ and $\omega = .70$ remain within Hair et al.'s (2010) acceptable range for early-stage research. These values align with the preliminary nature of this study and support continued examination of the External Orientation (E) factor in future research.

The CAS demonstrated acceptable EFA factor loadings ranging from .51 to .86, supporting the

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initial structure identified in this study. However, EFA alone cannot confirm the stability of the factor structure. Therefore, the CAS and its three-factor structure should be subject to further research using CFA, along with additional forms of validity testing to determine the scale's robustness. Despite these limitations, the current study's findings provide an essential first step toward validating the CAS as an instrument to measure CA orientation styles. The results demonstrate the potential for the CAS to operationalize the concepts of the CA orientation theory, offering a preliminary step toward examining how individuals may organize their experiences across the three building blocks.

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Table 1*Demographic Characteristics of Participants*

	<i>n</i>	<i>%</i>
Gender		
Female	259	71
Male	97	27
Transgender	4	1
Nonbinary	1	1
Marital status		
Single (never married)	59	16
Married	283	78
In a domestic partnership	27	7
Divorced	41	11
Widowed	6	2

None of these describe me

Ethnicity

White/Caucasian	316	88
Hispanic/Latino	14	4
Black/African American	18	5
Asian/Pacific Islander	10	2
Native American	1	.3
Jewish	1	.3
Multiracial	7	2
Prefer not to say	1	.3

Note. n = 361

Table 1 Continued

Demographic Characteristics of Participants

	<i>n</i>	<i>%</i>
<hr/>		
Education		
High school degree or equivalent	45	12
Associate degree	27	7
Trade School Degree	14	4
Bachelor's degree	89	24
Master's degree	152	42
Doctorate	34	9
Employment Status		
Employed full-time (40+ hours a week)	186	52
Employed part-time (less than 40 hours a week)	37	10
Employed multiple positions (greater than 40 hours a week)	11	3

Employed multiple positions (less than 40 hours a week)	5	1
Unemployed (currently not looking for work)	12	3
Unemployed (currently looking for work)	5	2
Student	9	2
Retired	25	7
Self-employed	71	20
I am a current client/patient of a mental health professional	136	38
I used to work with a mental health professional, but no longer do.	139	39
I have never worked with a mental health professional.	86	23

Note. n = 361

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics

	Emotional	Deep Feeler	Emotive	Sensitive	Logical	Rational	Reasoned	Analytical	Cooperative	Helpful	Agreeable	Considerate
Valid	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200
Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	3.07	3.34	2.91	3.20	3.23	3.27	3.18	2.86	3.34	3.58	3.28	3.51
Std. Deviation	0.78	0.84	0.84	0.74	0.70	0.64	0.60	0.91	0.65	0.57	0.61	0.60
Skewness	-0.31	-1.08	-0.24	-0.72	-0.70	-0.42	-0.23	-0.40	-0.59	-0.98	-0.36	-0.97
Std. Error of Skewness	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17
Kurtosis	-0.75	0.26	-0.73	0.38	0.51	-0.11	0.28	-0.66	-0.13	-0.04	0.11	0.67
Std. Error of Kurtosis	0.34	0.34	0.34	0.34	0.34	0.34	0.34	0.34	0.34	0.34	0.34	0.34
Minimum	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	2.00	1.00	1.00
Maximum	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00

Note. n = 361

Table 3*EFA Factor Loadings*

	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	
	Sensation (S)	Mental (M)	External (E)	Uniqueness
	Orientation	Orientation	Orientation	
Emotional	0.84			0.29
Deep Feeler	0.73			0.48
Emotive	0.68			0.55
Sensitive	0.57			0.67
Logical		0.86		0.27
Rational		0.65		0.5
Reasoned		0.63		0.58
Analytical		0.56		0.71
Cooperative			0.69	0.55
Helpful			0.61	0.6
Agreeable			0.60	0.66
Considerate			0.51	0.65

Note. Applied rotation method is ProMax.

Figure 1

Theoretical Organization of the Three Principles of Constructed Awareness

Principle 1: Bringing awareness to a client's experience changes their experience

Principle 2: The human experience is comprised of three building blocks: mental, sensation, and external

Principle 3: Most clients naturally rely more strongly on one of the three building blocks in certain situations

Note. Each orientation style is indicated by a three-letter code, where M = the mental building block, S = the sensation building block, and E = the external building block. MES = mental, external, sensation; MSE = mental, sensation, external; SME = sensation, mental, external; SEM = sensation, external, mental; EMS = external, mental, sensation; ESM = external, sensation, mental. The order reflects which building blocks the client relies on most to least.

Figure 2

The Constructed Awareness Typology

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Figure 3

Scree Plot of Eigenvalues for the Constructed Awareness Scale

Note. The scree plot displays the eigenvalues associated with each factor extracted in the EFA. The point of inflection indicates a three-factor solution, consistent with the theoretical model of the CAS.